

Preparation of New Azole and Pyrimidine Derivatives

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Azoles and pyrimidines have various uses¹. In continuation of our work, we report here the preparation of new monocyclic and fused pyrazole derivatives. 5-Chloro-3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-4-carboxaldehyde has been condensed with different moieties having active methylene groups to give unsaturated compounds. Monocyclic or fused pyrazolo[3,4-*d*]pyrazole, isoxazole and [3,4-*d*]pyrimidinone derivatives were prepared by their reaction with hydrazine, urea or thiourea.

Condensation of the formyl compound² (1) with 3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-one, 2-methyloxazolone and acetophenones in ethanol using different basic catalysts afforded the α,β -unsaturated compounds (2-4). The mass spectrum of 4a showed molecular ion-peak at m/z 322 with clear isotopic pattern of the chlorine atom. Its ¹H nmr spectrum showed no absorption at δ 9.0-10.0 indicating the disappearance of the aldehydic group, but revealed signals at δ 6.15-6.3 due to protons of the conjugated double bond.

The activation exerted by the carbonyl group on the exocyclic double bond renders compounds 2-4 suitable for condensation with hydrazines. Their reaction with hydrazine hydrate, phenylhydrazine, hydroxylamine hydrochloride, urea and thiourea separately afforded the corresponding monocyclic or fused 5-chloro-3-methyl-1-phenyl-pyrazol-4-yl derivatives of *N*-acetyl- or *N*-phenylpyrazole, isoxazole and pyrimidinones respectively. The structures of these compounds were established through analytical and, in a few cases, spectral data.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr)

were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 127B spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian EM 360 spectrometer (60 MHz) using TMS as internal standard and mass spectra on a Mat 311 instrument (70 eV). All reactions were monitored by tlc.

3-Methyl-4-(5-chloro-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methylene-1-phenyl-4,5-dihydropyrazol-5-

one (2) : To a solution of the formyl compound (1.3 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml), an ethanolic solution of 3-methyl-1-phenylpyrazol-5-one (2.6 g, 0.01 mol) and a catalytic amount of piperidine were added, then refluxed for 10 h, concentrated and cooled. The resulting brownish solid was crystallised from DMF/H₂O, (80%) m.p. 185–87°; ν_{\max} 1730 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 1.29 (6H, s, 2Me), 4.8 (1H, s, C-5-H), 7.1–7.8 (10H, m, ArH); *m/z* 376 (100), 172 (40).

2-Methyl-4-(5-chloro-3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)methylene-4,5-dihydro-oxazol-5-one (3) : A mixture of equimolar amounts of **1** and 2-methyloxazolone was refluxed in ethanol for 6 h in presence of a few drops of piperidine, then cooled and the resulting pale brownish solid was crystallised from dilute methanol, (75%), m.p. 190–93°; ν_{\max} 1725 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 1.28–1.35 (6H, s, 2Me), 4.75 (1H, s, C-5-H), 7.1–7.8 (5H, m, ArH); *m/z* 301 (100), 171 (60).

5-Chloro-3-methyl-4-yl(α,β -unsaturated-arylketo-*ne*)-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole (4a-c) : A mixture of equimolar amounts of **1** and 4-substituted acetophenone was refluxed in ethanolic KOH for 8–10 h, then concentrated, cooled, diluted with H₂O/HCl and the resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol as pale brown crystals : **4a** (75%), m.p. 115–17°; ν_{\max} 1730 (C=O); δ 1.3 (3H, s, Me), 6.15 (1H, d, C-5-H), 6.3 (1H, d, C-6-H, *J*_{5,6} 7 Hz); *m/z* 322 (100), 173 (30); **4b** (80%), 180–83°; ν_{\max} 1735 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 1.3 (3H, s, Me), 6.1 (1H, d, C-5-H), 6.25 (1H, c, C-6-H, *J*_{5,6} 7 Hz), 7.1–8.3 (9H, m, ArH); *m/z* 367 (100), 173 (20); **4c** (65%), 160–64°; ν_{\max} 1735 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 1.3 (3H, s, Me), 3.8 (3H, s, OMe), 6.1 (1H, d, C-5-H), 6.2 (1H, d, C-6-H, *J*_{5,6} 7 Hz), 7.1–7.6 (9H, m, ArH); *m/z* 352 (100), 171 (30).

General procedure for reaction of 2 with hydrazines : Separate reactions of equimolar amounts of **2** and hydrazine hydrate in boiling ethanol/acetic acid, phenylhydrazine in presence of piperidine, hydroxylamine hydrochloride in ethanolic NaOH (0.3 *N*), urea and thiourea in ethanolic HCl (0.01 *N*) afforded the corresponding derivatives of *N*-acetylpyrazoline (**5a**) (after acylation), *N*-phenylpyrazoline (**5b**), isoxazoline (**5c**), pyrimidine (**6a**) and pyrimidine thione (**6b**) respectively : **5a** (80%), m.p. 200–30°, greenish yellow (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1690 cm⁻¹ (C=O);

δ 1.2 (6H, s, 2Me), 2.2 (3H, s, Me-CO), 5.1–5.3 (2H, d, *J* 11 Hz, pyraz.), 7.22–7.9 (10H, m, ArH); *m/z* 432 (70); **5b** (70%), 160–62°, brownish (EtOH); ν_{\max} , 1610 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 1.2 (6H, s, 2Me), 5.9–6.2 (2H, d, *J* 11 Hz, pyraz.), 7.1–7.9 (15H, m, ArH); *m/z* 466 (80); **5c** (50%), 205–07°; pale brownish (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1615 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 1.2 (6H, s, 2Me), 5.1–5.2 (2H, d, *J* 11 Hz, pyraz.), 7.1–7.8 (10H, m, 2 × ArH); *m/z* 391 (70); **6a** (70%), 230–33°, greenish brown (DMF/H₂O); ν_{\max} 1740 (C=O), 3400–3300 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 1.2 (6H, s, 2Me), 3.4 (1H, b, NH), 7.1–7.9 (10H, m, ArH); *m/z* 418 (80); **6b** (73%), m.p. 210–12°, greenish (DMF/H₂O); ν_{\max} 1213 (C=S), 3400–3300 cm⁻¹ (NH); δ 1.2 (6H, s, 2Me), 3.4 (1H, b, NH), 7.1–7.8 (10H, m, ArH); *m/z* 434 (60).

The reaction of the unsaturated compound (**3**) and the hydrazines was performed as mentioned above affording compounds **7a-c**, **8a, b**: **7a** (80%), m.p. 220–23°, pale brown (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1620 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 1.2–1.3 (6H, s, 2Me), 2.3 (3H, s, Me-CO), 5.1–5.4 (2H, d, *J* 9.2 Hz, pyraz.) 7.3–7.8 (5H, m, ArH); *m/z* 357 (80); **7b** (85%), 185–87°, pale brown (EtOH); **7c** (50%) 215–17°, pale brown (EtOH); **8a** (60%), 235–38° brown (DMF/H₂O); ν_{\max} 1710 cm⁻¹ (C=O); δ 1.2 (3H, s, Me), 1.25 (3H, s, Me), 3.5 (1H, b, NH), 7.3–7.8 (5H, m, ArH); *m/z* 344 (75); **8b** (60%), 245–47°, brown (DMF).

Products from the reaction of 4a-c with hydrazines, hydroxylamine, urea or thiourea : Separate reactions of compounds **4a-c** (0.1 mol) and hydrazine hydrate in presence of a few drops of acetic acid, phenylhydrazine with piperidine, hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 ml) in 0.3 *M* alcoholic NaOH solution, urea or thiourea in presence of 0.05 *M* HCl under refluxing condition in ethanol for 5–10 h were carried out. The *N*-acetylated products (**9a**, **11a**, **13a**) were obtained by adding a few drops of cold water to the concentrated reaction mixture followed by acetylation. However, the *N*-phenylpyrazolines (**9b**, **11b**, **13b**), isoxazolines (**9c**, **11c**, **13c**) and pyrimidinones (**10a,b**, **12a,b**, **14a,b**) were obtained by neutralisation of the concentrated reaction mixture with acetic acid, hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide solution respectively. All these products were purified by crystallisation from suitable solvents : **9a** (70%), m.p. 140–42°, brown (EtOH);

NOTE

ν_{\max} 1720 cm^{-1} (C=O); δ 1.2 (3H, s, Me), 2.2 (3H, s, Me-CO), 5.1–5.15 (2H, d, J 10 Hz, pyraz.), 5.2 (1H, t, pyraz.), 7.1–7.8 (10H, m, ArH); m/z 378 (50); **9b** (75%), 130–32°, brown (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1615 cm^{-1} (C=C); δ 1.2 (3H, s, Me), 5.1–5.15 (2H, d, J 12 Hz, pyraz.), 5.2 (1H, t, pyraz.), 7.1–7.8 (15H, m, ArH); m/z 412 (70); **9c** (60%), 160–62°, yellow (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1610 cm^{-1} (C=C); m/z 337 (80); **10a** (60%) 140–43°, brown (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1715 (C=O), 3400–3300 cm^{-1} (NH); m/z 364 (65); **10b** (60%), 160–63°, brown (EtOH); **11a** (70%), 165–68°, yellow (EtOH); ν_{\max} 1680 cm^{-1} (C=O); m/z 423 (60); **11b** (60%), 120–23°, yellow brown (MeOH); **11c** (75%), 210–12°, brown (DMF); **12a** (45%), 160–63°, orange brown (MeOH); ν_{\max} 1710 (C=O), 3400–3300 cm^{-1} (NH); m/z 409 (70); **12b**, (50%), 170–72°, pale orange (MeOH); **13a** (70%),

180–83°, brown (MeOH); ν_{\max} 1620 cm^{-1} (C=C); m/z 408 (65); **13b** (60%), 210–13°, brown (DMF); **13c** (62%), 175–77°, brown (MeOH); **14a** (74%), 232–34°, pale brown (DMF); ν_{\max} 1715 (C=O), 3400–3300 cm^{-1} (NH); m/z 394 (70); **14b** (60%), 185–87°, brown (EtOH).

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